

Packaging influence in optical analysis of minimally processed and ready to eat *Valerianella locusta* L. by visible/near-infrared (vis/NIR) spectroscopy to monitor shelf life

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The availability of a nondestructive instrument allowing the monitoring of shelf life for fresh-cut fruits and vegetables could have a wide range of practical applications in the chain: during the storage period before packaging, during the production process for identifying critical points, and during the distribution post-packaging chain, the most critical phase. Furthermore, the possibility to implement nondestructive technology for monitoring product freshness at the point of sale should be a guarantee for consumers. The aim of this work was to investigate the applicability of visible/near-infrared (vis/NIR) for evaluating packaging influence on the measurements during freshness decay monitoring of minimally processed and ready-to-eat *Valerianella* (*Valerianella locusta* L.) leaves. The shelf-life of *Valerianella* leaf was monitored using a portable commercial vis/NIR spectrophotometer ranged from 350 nm to 2500 nm. *Valerianella* samples were stored at 4 °C for 14 days, and 10 sampling points were planned: five sampling dates before and five sampling dates after the expiration date. Spectra were acquired in reflectance mode through packaging. To test the performance of optical analysis on closed salad bag, a comparison on 10 leaves without packaging was performed. Due to the sample thinness, a dark or a white surface was placed on the opposite side of the leaf, corresponding to the acquisition point, to also evaluate the best background setting. Principal component analysis (PCA) was performed to analyse the spectral data in order to evaluate the influence of the packaging and verify a reasonable sample grouping according to the shelf-life evolution of *Valerianella* samples. Preliminary exploratory results were encouraging, showing that the potential influence of the head space between the film and product surface tend to cancel out. These findings would be useful in the development of freshness decay assessment tools using this optical technique along products' post-packaging chain.

Keywords: post-harvest, vegetables, freshness, baby-leaf, qualitative analysis, packaging film

REFERENCES

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